

SITE GS/S	DATE 6/21/79	AREA NE	SQUARE N3/W1	PAGE
	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top: 10.63	Bottom: 10.495
	DIMENSIONS			
Feature No.	Diameter: 12-15 cm	Width: 12-15 cm top	Length: (Round)	Depth: 14 cm

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions		
1	SAND	Light Greyish- Brown	Packed	Fine	T	Lm 2 Frag.; Flecks	Gp	
					D	2	Gr	Char 1 Frag.
						0	Do	
							Ba	
	Al							
						Other Thin fiber strands under charcoal		
					T	Lm	Gp	
					D	Gr	Char	
						Do		
						Ba		
	Al							
						Other		
					T	Lm	Gp	
					D	Gr	Char	
						Do		
						Ba		
	Al							
						Other		
					T	Lm	Gp	
					D	Gr	Char	
						Do		
						Ba		
	Al							
						Other		
					T	Lm	Gp	
					D	Gr	Char	
						Do		
						Ba		
	Al							
						Other		

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ 1	No./ 6, 7	B&W: 1 Roll/	No./ 6, 7
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DRAWN	Area Plan: Plotted 1:50 NE	Feature Plan:	Sections: 1:1 Section w Fill
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: Does fiber indicate mod. fill? After S.H. Excavation?
After NS 78?
1 of 2 small sherds lying on surface of fill